

Inclusion and social justice: Possibilities of mathematics education in the context with immigrants

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This article presents a doctoral research project that relates to the theme of inclusion and social justice from the perspective of critical mathematics education. The research aims at reflections beyond the school environment by researching immigrants and mathematics teachers from São Paulo State. In a qualitative methodological approach, interviews will be conducted, and comments will be made through a diary of notes. It is hoped that this research can contribute to the construction of critical perspectives on how mathematics education can be structured towards the inclusion of immigrant students and help to promote anti-racist mathematics education.

The theoretical frameworks

This doctoral research starts from concerns around issues related to immigration by dealing with themes of inclusion and social justice. According to the United Nations (UN) International Migration Inventory, in 2019, around 3.5% of the population on the planet were people who lived in countries other than the countries where they were born. Considering this amount, one in seven international migrants (about 38 million) are under the age of 20, which represents many school-age people.

International migrants are often faced with borders that can be material or immaterial. Material borders can be the concrete walls themselves, for example, which are placed as barriers, such as restrictions on mobility for immigrants. But also, the anti-immigration policies that are the subject of speeches by governments in different countries. Immaterial borders, on the other hand, are barriers that are often imperceptible or disregarded, such as those that appear during displacements in which people are subjected to precarious and dangerous modes of transport in crossings between countries. At the destination location, language barriers, customs, local laws, cultural differences, barriers to documentation, longing for the country of origin, barriers in the relationship with the local population, xenophobic speeches (whether recreational in jokes or more explicitly), also characterize immaterial boundaries.

In Brazil, the historical constitution of the population is also marked by international migrations, whether they are voluntary or forced. Amid the myth of racial democracy and

Please cite as: Carrijo, M. H. S. (2021). Inclusion and social justice: Possibilities of mathematics education in the context with immigrants. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 141–144). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5387644>

migratory receptivity, research, and media show that migratory receptivity is often selective, that is, it may be related to the physical characteristics or the country of origin of immigrants. The myth of racial democracy distorts the real reality that racism in Brazil is structural and encompasses the reality of immigrants in the country today (Almeida, 2019).

In this text, racism is understood as a historical and social construction. As a systematic form of discrimination that gives a specific ethnic group a place of dominance over others. In other words, it is a systematic way of producing disadvantages and privileges depending on the group to which people belong (Almeida, 2019). In the context of immigrants, racism works more broadly and goes beyond the model of racism based on the black / white binary. It can be based on discrimination based on phenotype (visible characteristics of people's bodies), accent, geographic origin, religion, customs, and immigration situations.

In the face of diversified environments generated by migration, it is important that anti-racist practices are present inside and outside the school context. Therefore, the connection between tolerance and social and racial justice is fundamental. When talking about social and racial justice, it is necessary to recognize the existence of racism, to consider reparation for inequalities of opportunity, to question arguments based on meritocracy and to reflect policies of racial equality (Martin, 2013).

According to Gutstein (2006), mathematics education has the role of helping structurally marginalized groups to investigate and question injustices, such as racism and other social inequalities. Therefore, it is important to guide students to engage in the quest to challenge and transform structures of oppression. For the author, teaching mathematics for social justice is also teaching mathematics for racial justice. "This includes providing students with opportunities to analyze whether and how racism is implicated in social phenomena and to understand different forms of racism." (Gutstein, 2016, p. 490). In this context, it also includes rethinking the context of international migration and reflecting differences in the classroom.

For Skovsmose (2016), critical mathematics education has concerns with different groups of students and is relevant to teaching and learning about issues of social injustice and oppression. These concerns contribute to the organization of environments that favor inclusion and tolerance. Thinking about these environments with immigrant students requires considering social justice and racial justice, and the encounter between differences.

According to the UN (1995), education policies and programs must contribute to an understanding of solidarity, tolerance among ethnic, social, cultural, religious, and linguistic groups between nations. Tolerance, as defended by Freire (2017), is not a favor from the tolerant to the tolerated, in the sense of class, race, gender superiority. Nevertheless, tolerance is a virtue of human coexistence, of living with the different and not with the inferior.

Thus, the question of this research is: *How is mathematics education structured for the inclusion of immigrant students?* This research seeks to understand the context of immigration in Brazil and around the world, to reflect the connection between racism and xenophobia and to discuss possibilities for an inclusive mathematical education in the context of immigrants.

Research planning

This investigation perceives the complexity of the social, historical, and political context when working with social phenomena and the subjects involved in them, and in this way, this investigative process uses a qualitative approach to research.

It is also based on the assumptions of the Critical Race Theory (CRT) (Davis & Jett, 2019). For this reason, it gives special importance to the voice of people who are racially minorized through their reports and narratives about their lived experiences. It considers various forms of injustice and explores differences within and between groups when considering the historical and political context together with an awareness of racial inequalities.

In this sense, the data production of this research will be developed in the following moments: Interview with immigrants in which the following points will be considered: about the context of the immigrant family; about inequality / about exclusion / about social and racial justice; situation as a student / school context; about racism and xenophobia. Interviews with mathematics teachers and school managers in which the following points will be considered: context of immigrant students / context of schools with immigrant students/ about inequality, exclusion and social and racial justice/ about the role of mathematics in the context of immigration /about and racism and xenophobia/ about possibilities in mathematics classes in the context of immigrant students.

According to the data produced, we will point out research results in the light of Critical Mathematical Education (Skovsmose, 2019). The interviews will be recorded in audio and video. These moments will be transcribed and supplemented with notes made by the researcher that will contain memories of the context of the speeches, the atmosphere of the discussions, the episodes of silence, elements of the interactions between the researcher and the research participant, constituting information for the understanding and interpretation of the theme. There will be a reflection on the interaction of the materials and attention to the contents as official documents, responses to the production instruments, and to the content as elements of the social life of the participants, context of the countries of immigrants, context of Brazil, among others.

Comments

This research aims at reflections beyond classroom environments. It is hoped that the realization of this research can contribute to debates on the teaching and learning of mathematics and describe possibilities for actions that seek to promote contributions to an anti-racist and inclusive mathematical education in the context of immigrants. More broadly, favor conditions to combat social inequalities and injustices.

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M. H. S. Carrijo

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